

AN EXAMINATION OF ART LITERACY LEVELS OF PROSPECTIVE CLASSROOM TEACHERS

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Abstract:

This research aims to examine the art literacy levels of prospective classroom teachers according to their grades, gender, whether they like reading art books and whether they like doing research in the library. A total of 148 prospective classroom teachers (103 females and 45 males) at the third and fourth grades in the department of classroom teaching at Niğde Ömer Halisdemir University constitute the sample of the research. The " Art Literacy Scale" developed by Yücetoker (2014) was used as the data collection tool. This research has been designed in the causal-comparative model. Independent group t-test and one-way variance analysis techniques were used for the data analysis. At the end of the research, no significant difference was found between art literacy levels in terms of grade. In terms of gender, there was no significant difference in using art literacy information, defining information needs, transferring information to performance, but there is a significant difference in reaching art literacy information. Male students' levels of reaching art literacy information were found to be higher than that of female students. In terms of whether they like reading art books, there was a significant difference in using information, describing the need for information, and transferring information to performance but there was no significant difference in reaching art literacy information. In terms of liking to do research in the library, there was no significant difference in using art literacy information, describing the need for information and reaching information while the level of transferring art literacy information to performance was found to be higher in students who are interested in doing research in the library.

Keywords: literacy, art literacy, prospective classroom teacher

1. Introduction

Literacy can be defined in many different ways, and these definitions are constantly changing. For example, literacy sometimes includes only reading, sometimes reading

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and writing, and rarely reading, writing, speaking and listening. Literacy is also described as the ability to read and write at an appropriate level of fluency. (Inglis & Aers, 2008).

An individual's ability to read and write by understanding short and simple expressions about daily life is called literacy. (Keefe, E. B. & Copeland R. S. 2011). Literacy means that an individual engages in reading or writing in any case and whether alone or not at home, at school, at work or elsewhere and that these actions are used in a social context. The social context in this definition emphasizes that literacy is constructive and dynamic rather than static. (Au, 2000, cited by Gül, 2007).

Today, literacy concepts are used in many scientific researches. These concepts include information literacy, science literacy, visual literacy, media literacy, environmental literacy, information literacy, music literacy and art literacy.

Information literacy is the skill of finding, evaluating and using information effectively and efficiently in both individual and professional life. (Mc Clark, 1991, cited by Gürdal, 2000).

Science literacy means being familiar with the natural world and recognizing both its diversity and its unity, knowing the key concepts and principles of science, being aware of some important links connecting science, mathematics and technology, understanding that science, mathematics and technology are the product of human efforts, recognizing the strengths and limitations that this brings to those areas and having scientific thinking capacity. (Kaptan, 1999). It can be inferred from this that scientific literacy means having scientific information as well as scientific skills and attitudes. (Kesik, 2016).

Visual literacy is shortly defined as the power to understand and create visual messages. (Heinich, Molenda and Russel, 1989, cited by, Alpan-Bangir, 2008). Media literacy can be described as the ability to reach, analyze and communicate media messages. Media literacy training teaches the effects of globalization, economic balances and asking right questions rather than finding answers in information pollution. It is also an education that enables students to gain perspectives that will enable them to be strong against media culture throughout their lives. (Tallim, 2010). Media literate individual can make a critical analysis of media messages and have the will to choose among different media and programs. (Gündüz-Kalan, 2008).

Environmental literacy is the whole of understanding, knowledge, skills and attitudes improving the behavior of individuals about their own environment and enabling them to engage in daily and long-term actions in a sustainable environment with other individuals and relationships with nature. Environmental literacy is about seeking answers to the questions that we ask regarding our environment and using these answers efficiently. (Roth, 2002; Cited by Timur B., Yılmaz & Timur S., 2014).

Information literacy can shortly be defined as the ability to access, evaluate and use information effectively during problem solving and decision-making. The programs to be prepared by trainers and librarians aiming to provide information literacy skills to students at formal education institutions will show the usefulness of information

literacy for individuals and communities and enable its dissemination to the masses. (Grdal, 2000).

Music literacy is the ability to understand most parts of a given traditional music. Music literacy also contributes to revealing the similarities and parallels between understanding music and reading the composition. (Levinson, 1990). Music literacy relates to the level of type of education at which music education is given and it can be defined as the whole of musical knowledge and application skills required to achieve the specified musical goals in that area. (Afacan, Őentrk, 2016).

Art literacy is a type of literacy that enables establishing an eclectic relationship between the local art perception in which the individual is directly involved and international arts which are accessed indirectly in the globalizing world, accessing the information that individuals in the art profession can need in their professional and individual lives and transferring this information to the applications of which the individual is the subject or an element. Based on this definition, students of fine arts should be able to transfer their national art to other international arts and make an evaluation of it. They should also be able to know where, when and how to reach all the information about the art, to use the information in the correct way and to easily convey the information they obtain to their performance. (Ycetoker, 2014).

Art literacy is individuals' developing interest and love for the fine arts and artworks. It is to have the basic information and skills necessary to express personal emotions and thoughts in the universal language of art. Short and long-term scientific researches carried out both in Turkey and in the world have revealed that all kinds of art works, especially music, make great contributions to cognitive and spiritual development of children. Art does not only allow children to know themselves, to express themselves, and to share with a creative language, it also improves children's problem-solving skills at an early age. (http://sanatseverturkiye.blogspot.com.tr/2012/02/sanat-okuryazarlg-nedir-sanat_26.html)

There has been an increasing interest in the field of art literacy in recent years. This is because some art related departments provide specific theoretical and practical courses in the education process. The goal can be said to transform the theoretical courses into practical lessons. For this reason, art literacy is an important type of literacy towards this goal. Art education course in classroom teaching departments include a view of art theories in the history of thought and philosophy, comprehending the theoretical and practical direction of knowledge and experience in the field of art, critical thinking and evaluation on art history and philosophy, interpreting the theories of art by using science and technology, educational functions of art, distinguishing the artwork from an industrial object, the ability to read works of different disciplines through artistic events and phenomena, acquiring information and experiences about the places where art works are exhibited, creativity concept, creative individual and their characteristics, creative thinking and artistic creation processes. There are very limited works on art literacy. From this point on, this research aims to examine the literacy levels of prospective classroom teachers.

2. Problem Statement

Examination of the art literacy levels of prospective classroom teachers is the problem statement of the research.

2.1 Sub Problems

1. Is there a significant difference in the art literacy levels of prospective classroom teachers in terms of their grades?
2. Is there a significant difference in the art literacy levels of prospective classroom teachers in terms of gender?
3. Is there a significant difference in the art literacy levels of prospective classroom teachers in terms of whether they like reading art books?
4. Is there a significant difference in the art literacy levels of prospective classroom teachers in terms of whether they like doing research in the library?

3. Method

2.1 The Research Model

Examining the art literacy levels of prospective classroom teachers in terms of gender, grade, whether they like reading art books, whether they like using libraries and reading frequency, this research was designed in the causal comparative model. Fraenkel, Wallen and Hyun (2011) stated that in a causal comparative research, researchers try to determine the cause or consequences of the differences between groups of individuals.

2.2 Universe and Sampling

The universe of the research consists of 3rd and Niğde mer Halisdemir The sample of the research consists of a total of 148 prospective classroom teachers (103 females and 45 males) at the 3rd and 4th grades enrolled in the Department of Elementary Education of the Education Faculty of Niğde mer Halisdemir University in 2017-2018 academic year.

2.3 Data Collection Tools

The "Art Literacy Scale", which was developed by Ycetoker (2014), was used as the data collection tool in the research. The art literacy scale consists of 26 items. The choices are scored as 5 for "I do not have any difficulty at all", 4 for "I do not have any difficulty", 3 for "I'm indecisive", 2 for "I have difficulty" and 1 for "I have a lot of difficulties". Since the questions in the scale were developed to find out the art literacy information of the students and whether they have difficulty in reaching this information, the questions were not grouped as negative or positive.

2.4 Analysis of Data

In the research, the first thing that was examined was whether there were missing values in the data set. These examinations showed that the three observations were incomplete. Missing data was completed by EM (Expectation Maximization) assignment method. Z scores were calculated to examine the extreme values in the data set and it was found that there was an observation with a score of over 3.29 in Z scores. This observation was removed from the dataset. For the normality hypothesis, skewness and kurtosis values and P-P plotgraph were examined. The skewness and kurtosis values were found to be close to 0 the data set was found to meet the normality hypothesis in the P-P plot graph. In line with these results, independent groups t-test and one-way variance analysis techniques were used for data analysis. The homogeneity of the variances from the hypothesis of the techniques used was tested and it was found that the variances were homogeneous. The margin of error in the research was accepted as .05.

3. Findings

In order to examine whether art literacy levels of prospective classroom teachers differed in terms of grade, gender, whether they like reading art books and whether they like using libraries, independent groups t-test technique was used and the findings were included in the following tables.

3.1 Findings regarding art literacy in terms of grade variable

Table 1a: Examination of using art literacy information in terms of grade

Grade	n	M	SS	t
3rd grade	76	32.26	6.53	.86
4th Grade	72	31.36	6.25	

There is no significant difference ($t(146) = .86, p > .05$) in the levels of reaching art literacy information in terms of whether they like doing research in the library. In other words, the level of using art literacy of third and fourth grade students in the classroom teaching department is similar.

Table 1b: Examining the level of defining the need for art literacy information in terms of grade

Grade	n	M	SS	t
3rd grade	76	16.71	3.34	.50
4th Grade	72	16.42	3.84	

There is no significant difference ($t(146) = .50, p > .05$) in the levels of reaching art literacy information in terms of whether they like doing research in the library. In other words, the levels of defining the need for art literacy information of third and fourth grade students in the classroom teaching department are similar to each other.

Table 1c: Examination of transferring art literacy information to performance in terms of grade

Grade	n	M	SS	t
3rd grade	76	19.95	4.69	.36
4th Grade	72	19.67	4.68	

There is no significant difference ($t(146)=.36, p>.05$) in the levels of reaching art literacy information in terms of whether they like doing research in the library. In other words, the levels of transferring art literacy information to performance of third and fourth-grade students in the classroom teaching department are similar to each other.

Table 1d: Examination of reaching art literacy information in terms of grade

Grade	n	M	SS	t
3rd grade	76	17.72	3.79	.29
4th Grade	72	17.54	3.84	

There is no significant difference ($t(146)=.29, p>.05$) in the levels of reaching art literacy information in terms of whether they like doing research in the library. In other words, the levels of reaching art literacy information of third and fourth grade students in the classroom teaching department are similar.

3.2 Findings regarding art literacy in terms of gender variable

Table 2a: Examination of using art literacy information in terms of gender

Gender	n	M	SS	t
Female	103	31.24	6.80	-1.69
Male	45	33.16	5.17	

There is no significant difference ($t(146)= -1.69, p>.05$) in the levels of reaching art literacy information in terms of whether they like doing research in the library. In other words, the levels of using art literacy information of female and male students are similar.

Table 2b: Examination of defining the need for art literacy information in terms of gender

Gender	n	M	SS	t
Female	103	16.27	3.75	-1.53
Male	45	17.24	3.09	

There is no significant difference ($t(146)= -1.55, p>.05$) in the levels of reaching art literacy information in terms of whether they like doing research in the library. In other words, the levels of defining the need for art literacy information of male and female students are similar.

Table 2c: Examination of transferring art literacy information to performance in terms of gender

Gender	n	M	SS	t
Female	103	19.45	4.75	-1.44
Male	45	20.64	4.41	

There is no significant difference ($t(146) = -1.44, p > .05$) in the levels of reaching art literacy information in terms of whether they like doing research in the library. In other words, the levels of transferring art literacy information to performance of female and male students are similar.

Table 2d: Examination of reaching art literacy information in terms of gender

Gender	n	M	SS	t
Female	103	17.11	3.83	-2.56*
Male	45	18.22	3.50	

* $p < .05$

There is a significant difference ($t(146) = -2.56, p < .05$) in the levels of transferring art literacy information to performance in terms of whether they like doing research in the library. Male students have higher levels of reaching art literacy information than female students.

3.3 Findings regarding art literacy in terms of whether they like reading art books

Table 3a: Examination of using art literacy information in terms of whether they like reading art books

Whether they like reading art books	n	M	SS	t
Yes	55	34.15	6.58	3.53*
No	93	30.45	5.89	

* $p < .05$

There is a significant difference ($t(146) = 3.53, p < .05$) in the levels of transferring art literacy information to performance in terms of whether they like doing research in the library. In other words, the students who like reading art books have a higher level of using art literacy information than those who do not like.

Table 3b: Examination of defining the need for art literacy information in terms of whether they like reading art books

Whether they like reading art books	n	M	SS	t
Yes	55	18	3.47	3.92*
No	93	15.72	3.38	

* $p < .05$

There is a significant difference ($t(146) = 3.92, p < .05$) in the levels of transferring art literacy information to performance in terms of whether they like doing research in the library. In other words, the students who like reading art books have higher levels of defining the need for art literacy information than those who do not like.

Table 3c: Examination of transferring art literacy information to performance in terms of whether they like reading art books

Whether they like reading art books	n	M	SS	t
Yes	55	21.40	4.85	3.29*
No	93	18.87	4.32	

* $p < .05$

There is a significant difference ($t(146) = 3.29, p < .05$) in the levels of transferring art literacy information to performance in terms of whether they like doing research in the library. In other words, the students who like reading art books have a higher level of transferring art literacy information to performance than those who do not like.

Table 3d: Examination of reaching art literacy information in terms of whether they like reading art books

Whether they like reading art books	n	M	SS	t
Yes	55	18.42	3.71	1.94
No	93	17.17	3.80	

There is no significant difference ($t(146) = 1.94, p > .05$) in the levels of reaching art literacy information in terms of whether they like doing research in the library. In other words, the levels of reaching art literacy information of the students who like and dislike reading art books are similar.

3.4 Findings regarding art literacy in terms of whether they like doing research in the library

Table 4a: Examination of using art literacy information in terms of whether they like doing research in the library

Whether they like doing research in the library	n	M	SS	t
Yes	89	32.63	6.72	1.90
No	59	30.61	5.70	

There is no significant difference ($t(146) = 1.90, p > .05$) in the levels of using art literacy information in terms of whether they like doing research in the library. In other words, the levels of using art literacy information of the students who like and dislike doing research in the library are similar.

Table 4b: Examination of defining the need for art literacy information in terms of whether they like doing research in the library

Whether they like doing research in the library	n	M	SS	t
Yes	89	16.94	3.68	1.58
No	59	16	3.37	

There is no significant difference ($t(146) = 1.58, p > .05$) in the levels of reaching art literacy information in terms of whether they like doing research in the library. In other words,

the levels of defining the need for art literacy information of students who like and dislike doing research in the library are similar.

Table 4c: Examination of transferring art literacy information to performance in terms of whether they like doing research in the library

Whether they like doing research in the library	n	M	SS	t
Yes	89	20.54	4.91	2.37*
No	59	18.71	4.09	

* $p < .05$

There is a significant difference ($t(146) = 2.37, p < .05$) in the levels of transferring art literacy information to performance in terms of whether they like doing research in the library. In other words, students who are interested in doing research in the library have a higher level of transferring art literacy information to performance than those who are not interested.

Table 4d: Examination of reaching art literacy information in terms of whether they like doing research in the library

Whether they like doing research in the library	n	M	SS	t
Yes	89	17.92	3.89	1.13
No	59	17.20	3.65	

There is no significant difference ($t(199) = 1.13, p > .05$) in the levels of reaching art literacy information in terms of whether they like doing research in the library. In other words, among students of classroom teaching, the levels of reaching art literacy information are similar between those who like and do not like doing research in the library.

4.5 Findings regarding art literacy in terms of grade variable

In order to find out whether there is a significant difference in using art literacy information, defining the need for art literacy information, transferring art literacy information to performance and reaching art literacy information in terms of reading frequency, one way analysis of variance (One Way Anova) technique was used and the results are given below.

Table 5a: Examination of art literacy in terms of reading frequency

Dimension	Reading Frequency	n	M	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	sv	Mean of Squares	F
Using art literacy information	1. Everyday	17	34.94	Intergroups	369.59	4	92.40	2.34
	2. Once a week	24	31.25					
	3. Twice a week	26	33.69	Intragroups	5633.84	143	39.40	
	4. Once a month	55	30.49	Total	6003.43	147		
	5. Never	26	31.27					

There was no significant difference ($F(4, 143) = 2.34, p > .05$) in the levels of using art literacy information in terms of reading frequency. In other words, the levels of using art literacy information of classroom teachers are similar in terms of reading frequency.

Table 5b: Examination of defining information need
for art literacy in terms of frequency of reading books

Dimension	Reading Frequency	n	M	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	sv	Mean of Squares	F
Defining the need for art literacy information	1. Everyday	17	17.65	Intergrroups	90.11	4	22.53	1.80
	2. Once a week	24	16.50					
	3. Twice a week	26	17.77	Intragroups	1794.22	143	12.55	
	4. Once a month	55	15.81	Total	1884.33	147		
	5. Never	26	16.31					

In terms of reading frequency, there is no significant difference ($F(4, 143)= 1.80, p> .05$) in the level of reaching art literacy information in terms of reading frequency. In terms of reading frequency, the levels of defining the need for art literacy information of classroom teaching students are similar.

Table 5c: Examination of transferring art literacy knowledge
into performance in terms of frequency of reading books

Dimension	Reading Frequency	n	M	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	sv	Mean of Squares	F
Transferring art literacy information to performance	1. Everyday	17	21.94	Intergrroups	151.80	4	37.95	1.78
	2. Once a week	24	20					
	3. Twice a week	26	20.65	Intragroups	3052.91	143	21.35	
	4. Once a month	55	19.24	Total	3204.71	147		
	5. Never	26	18.62					

In terms of reading frequency, there was no significant difference ($F(4, 143)= 1.78, p> .05$) in the level of transferring art literacy information to performance. In terms of reading frequency, the levels of transferring art literacy information to performance of classroom teaching students are similar.

Table 5d: Examination of reaching art literacy information
in terms of frequency of reading books

Dimension	Reading Frequency	n	M	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	sv	Mean of Squares	F
Reaching art literacy information	1. Everyday	17	18.71	Intergrroups	60.65	4	15.16	1.05
	2. Once a week	24	17.54					
	3. Twice a week	26	18.42	Intragroups	2063.65	143	14.43	
	4. Once a month	55	16.96	Total	2124.30	147		
	5. Never	26	17.65					

There is no significant difference ($F(4, 143)=1.05, p> .05$) in the level of reaching art literacy information in terms of reading frequency. In terms of reading frequency, the levels of reaching art literacy information of classroom teaching students are similar.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

The results of the research carried out have been given below.

1. There is no significant difference in the level of using art literacy information in terms of grade variable. In other words, the levels of using art literacy information of the third and fourth grade classroom teaching students are similar.
2. There is no significant difference in the level of defining the need for art literacy in terms of grade variable. In other words, the levels of defining the need for art literacy information of third and fourth grade students in the classroom teaching department are similar to each other.
3. There is no significant difference in the level of transferring art literacy information to performance in terms of grade variable. In other words, the levels of transferring art literacy information to performance of third and fourth-grade students in the classroom teaching department are similar to each other.
4. There is no significant difference in the level of reaching art literacy information in terms of grade variable. In other words, the levels of reaching art literacy information of third and fourth grade students in the classroom teaching department are similar.
5. There is no significant difference in the level of using art literacy information in terms of gender variable. In other words, the levels of using art literacy information of female and male students are similar.
6. There is no significant difference in the level of defining the need for art literacy information in terms of gender variable. In other words, the levels of defining the need for art literacy information of female and male students are similar.
7. There is no significant difference in the level of transferring art literacy information to performance in terms of gender variable. In other words, the levels of transferring art literacy information to performance of female and male students are similar.
8. There is a significant difference in the level of reaching art literacy information in terms of gender variable. Male students have higher levels of reaching art literacy information than female students. Looking at this fact, we might argue that male students are better at using computers and the Internet than girls.
9. There is a significant difference in the level of using art literacy information of classroom teaching students in terms of whether they like reading art books. In other words, the students who like reading art books have a higher level of using art literacy information than those who do not like.
10. There is a significant difference in the level of defining the need for art literacy information in terms of whether they like reading art books. In other words, the students who like reading art books have higher levels of defining the need for art literacy information than those who do not like.
11. There is a significant difference in the level of transferring art literacy information to performance in terms of whether they like reading art books. In

other words, the students who like reading art books have a higher level of transferring art literacy information to performance than those who do not like. This may imply that doing something with love is more important.

12. There is no significant difference in the level of reaching art literacy information in terms of whether they like reading art books. In other words, the levels of reaching art literacy information of the students who like and dislike reading art books are similar.
13. There is no significant difference in the level of using art literacy information of classroom teaching students in terms of whether they like doing research in the library. In other words, the levels of using art literacy information of the students who like and dislike doing research in the library are similar.
14. There is no significant difference in the level of defining the need for art literacy information in terms of whether they like doing research in the library. In other words, the levels of defining the need for art literacy information of students who like and dislike doing research in the library are similar.
15. There is a significant difference in the level of transferring art literacy information to performance in terms of whether they like doing research in the library. In other words, students who are interested in doing research in the library have a higher level of transferring art literacy information to performance than those who are not interested.
16. There is no significant difference in the level of reaching art literacy information in terms of whether they like doing research in the library. In other words, among students of classroom teaching, the levels of reaching art literacy information are similar between those who like and do not like doing research in the library.

The curriculum of the departments of classroom teaching of education faculties includes a theoretical course called Art Education at the second grade. This course allows students to conduct research in the library. However, it is considered that giving this course for only one semester is inadequate. Therefore, classroom teaching students cannot obtain a certain advantage in this area other than their own work or projects.

Course teachers should lead and support their students in doing research and transferring their information to performance. For a better understanding of artworks by seeing them in real life, teacher can make sure that students visit art galleries or museums. Students can be encouraged to perform artistic activities. Important art books can be provided by the art education teacher. Teachers can also ensure that students watch videos, conferences and seminars about art education, read articles and discuss on various topics related to art.

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